

Identifying Cochrane and non-Cochrane reviews relevant to your review topic

Before submitting the Review Proposal Form to EPOC, we ask authors to conduct searches for both Cochrane and non-Cochrane reviews on the proposed topic. The purpose is two-fold:

1. To prevent duplication of topics within the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR).
2. To identify the existing evidence-base in a topic area so that the proposed review topic builds on, but does not replicate published research.

Suggested sources to search

- Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR)
- [PDQ-Evidence](#) or [Health Systems Evidence](#)

For information about how to search PDQ-Evidence, see [How to use PDQ to identify systematic reviews and primary studies](#).

In addition you may want to search the following sources:

- Database of Abstracts of Reviews of Effects (DARE) either via The Cochrane Library or via the [CRD database](#)
- [PubMed](#) (use the Clinical Queries to limit your topic terms to systematic reviews)
- [Trip Database](#)

Please keep a record of the terms used to search each database as you will need to report these terms on the Review Proposal Form.

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). [Resource title]. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2017. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)